

INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS AT THE UNIVERSITY.

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Annotation: Innovative educational activities are currently one of the most important parts of educational activities of any institution. The main task of universities is to train specialists who can develop individual and timely solutions in a rapidly changing world. Innovative teaching methods are used to prepare the students for their future careers at the university. Prepare by requesting a comprehensive moral statement for the students of the common school.

Key words: innovative company, university, state company, consultancy, specialist, Czech state, scientific research, planning and supervision, preparation *byza* – this is a professional company.

University teaching is an art and a science. Art, because each activity is unique. Its emotional coloring and meaning depend on a number of factors, many of which are difficult to predict in advance. In this sense, teaching is like the work of an artist or a writer, which requires a deep knowledge of life, the human soul, the ability to see, understand and empathize. But at the same time, it is also a science based on objective laws that establishes essential connections and connections in the process of perception and assimilation of educational material. These laws act like supporting structures that enable the process of personality formation of a specialist [6]. The pedagogical activity of a university teacher includes pedagogical and methodological work, the organization of extracurricular activities, the management of study groups and the fulfillment of administrative tasks, such as B. the technical support of Internet resources, the maintenance of electronic documentation and the implementation of practical courses in an integrative environment [9]. Any teacher can master the teaching skills as long as they improve purposefully. These skills are developed based on practical experience. But not every experience becomes a source of professional skills. Such a source can only be work, understood from the point of view of its nature, goals and technology of activity. Pedagogical skills are a combination of a teacher's personal and business qualities and professional competencies. The development of teachers' professional competence has a significant impact on the formation of their desires and aspirations related to the improvement of their activities. This is primarily related to goal setting, the study of specific concepts and ideas, and an analysis of existing theories. The teacher can solve several problems at the same time, depending on which areas he/she is working on and what current needs arise. When choosing the means and ways to achieve the desired goal, the public interest must be taken into account. In the educational process, the teacher meets all those involved in this process (parents, representatives of non-governmental organizations) and on this basis the teacher's self-development occurs, and with it the development of his professional competence. The nature of the teacher's activity is influenced by the

requirements established by the state and society and as the educational system, the internal workings of the educational institution, the implementation of reforms in the country in the field of education, modern requirements for knowledge, skills and experience of a teacher, as well as knowledge of innovative technologies. The modernization of the educational process and environment encourages teachers to search for answers to their questions and encourages them to use creative approaches, which leads to the professional development of the teacher and the formation of his personal interests related to self-education and training. The creative, professional development of the teacher, in turn, has a positive effect on shaping the atmosphere of the educational institution. For the training of teachers' professional competence, it is also important to create an innovative environment based on creative collaboration that enables important problems to be solved together. The development of professional competence is a dynamic process of learning and improvement of work experience, which leads to the formation of individual professional qualities, which requires continuous development and self-improvement. The role of the teacher is traditionally defined by the function of imparting and activating knowledge and professional skills. This is now morphing into a high-level job of professional identity-building, aimed at instilling in students a willingness to acquire knowledge and improve their professional skills throughout their lives. In order to achieve high results in the practical professional activity of a university teacher, the goal of pedagogical training is indicated - the continuous general and professional development of a university teacher with high moral qualities, active participation in public life, with humanism, spirituality, morality, a critical attitude to their actions, the willingness to create new values and make creative decisions. The current level of development in education is characterized by an intensive search for new methods in theory and practice. This process is caused by a number of contradictions, the main reason of which is the incompatibility of traditional methods and forms of education and upbringing with new trends in the development of the educational system, as well as with modern socio-economic conditions for the development society, which many innovative produced objective processes. The innovative character of education becomes the most important tool in competition with other social institutions. In the current socio-economic situation, not only the content, but also the forms and technologies of education are important for the formation of a positive educational orientation among young people. The development of new teaching methods becomes an urgent need. Educational innovation is understood as a process of improving educational technologies, a set of methods, techniques and teaching materials. Innovative educational activities are currently one of the most important parts of the educational activities of every institution. Innovations are inextricably linked to the scientific and methodical work of the teachers and the teaching and research activities of the students. In the pedagogical process, innovative teaching methods ensure that innovations in the goals, methods, content and forms of training and further education are introduced into the joint activities of teachers and students. These innovations may be specially designed, already developed, or reintroduced as part of an educational initiative. Currently, the main task of universities is to educate professionals capable of developing individual, flexible and timely solutions in a rapidly changing world. To this end, innovative teaching methods are used to prepare students for a future career at the university. The practice of translation has always been controversial as to whether it can be an efficient and effective tool in learning a foreign language. Until recently, translation was not successful with teachers. As a language learning

activity, it was considered an inappropriate tool in the context of learning a foreign language. However, in recent decades there has been increasing interest in translation practice in foreign language teaching. Recently, foreign language teachers have revived the use of translation for various educational purposes. It was found that translation activities can be used together with other types of traditional language activities for pedagogical purposes and that translation as a method in language teaching practice contributes to a deeper insight into the substance of the material to be studied. Let's look at some of them. The portfolio method (performance portfolio or portfolio assessment) is a modern educational technology based on the method of reliable assessment of the results of educational and professional activities. Depending on the nature of the practical and productive activity of the higher education institution, educational and professional portfolios are distinguished. The problem presentation method is a method in which the teacher sets a task using various sources and means, formulates a cognitive task before presenting the material, and then identifies a system of evidence, compares viewpoints and different approaches, and presents a possibility ability to solve the problem. The project method is a learning system in which students acquire knowledge and skills in the process of planning and implementing increasingly complex practical task projects. Problem-seeking teaching methods (knowledge acquisition, competence development) are carried out in the process of partial search or research activities of the students; This method is implemented with the help of verbal, visual and practical teaching methods and interpreter with a view to formulating and solving a problem situation. One of the important criteria for studying a foreign language at a university is the ability to correctly translate any literature. This means that being able to do a correct translation from one language to another is an important and necessary art nowadays. Because every day a person in the specialist area is confronted with new terms or texts, the content of which could be used in professional activities. Student research work integrated into the educational process – this work is necessarily carried out in accordance with the curriculum; The results of all kinds of research activities of the students involved in the educational process are subject to the supervision and evaluation by the teacher. Problem-based learning is a technology that aims primarily to "create interest". Learning consists in creating problem situations, such situations in the joint action of students and teachers at optimal self-reliance. to recognize and solve student work and under the general guidance of a teacher; What is special about creative projects is that they do not have a predetermined and detailed structure. In a creative project, the teacher (coordinator) only sets the general parameters and indicates the best ways to solve the problem. A prerequisite for creative projects is a clear presentation of the planned result, which is important for students. Innovative methods have made it possible to change the role of the teacher, who is not only a carrier of knowledge, but also a mentor and initiates the creative search of the students. The learning process is an information system, because one of the main functions of learning is the transmission of information, knowledge and values to a new generation. Consequently, the laws characteristic of the information society is at work in it. The computer revolution, a significant increase in information and knowledge, shapes modern society, the so-called information society. According to information society theory, the sources of information and knowledge were mainly teachers and priests, but today it is teachers, textbooks and books, the media, the Internet, the students themselves, etc. They generate information and knowledge from a variety of sources. To maintain the integrity of the system, its replacement

is accelerated. Three key characteristics of information - novelty, dynamism and diversity - characterize society and modern education. The novelty lies in the renewal of educational paradigms; Updating the training content – both for each of the disciplines and with regard to the emergence of new disciplines; Updating of modules and teaching methods. The communication of a secondary language personality occurs in the form of continuous contacts of different language personalities, as a result of which there is a mutual enrichment of the language experience of the partners in communicative acts. In Russian, prepositions in combination with one or another case of nouns or other parts of speech clarifying syntactic functions, follow in the sentence the control word expressed by the verb. In the Uzbek language, controlled-word verbs require the appropriate case form of nouns in combination with a postposition. Since the connection between words in phrases and sentences of the Russian language occurs via case suffixes, postpositions, service names (in the corresponding case forms) and a certain word order (in some cases) [2, p. 26]. A major difficulty for students is the correct use of prepositions in the Russian language in the process of high-quality translation. Dynamism determines the speed of knowledge renewal, the acceleration of the learning process itself, the exchange of information in the learning process, etc. Translation as a method of teaching Russian as a non-native language is still a subject of research and remains one of the most frequently discussed topics linguists, methodologists and teachers. However, the present study shows that translation activities are a useful educational tool. When translation is purposefully and creatively integrated into a language learning program, it becomes an appropriate method of language practice for many learners. When integrated into daily classroom activities, translation can help learners to develop and improve their reading, speaking, writing, grammar and vocabulary skills. Translation in foreign language lessons contributes to a better understanding of the structures of both languages and also strengthens translation skills. It is an effective and efficient tool for learning a foreign language. However, the translation practice in the classroom should not be overused and should be intelligently integrated into the language lessons together with other teaching aids. Diversity means the diversification of education, which is reflected in diversification of educational institutions, funding sources, and diversification of curricula, programs, and courses. Thus, novelty, dynamism and diversity as key characteristics of information directly affect the methods and forms of learning. The novelty requires constant updating of the teaching and seminar content as well as the teaching methods and forms. Therefore, with the advent of information technology (IT) and the opening of companies, the teaching methods are updated thanks to the emergence of new IT-based teaching methods and their significant influx of foreign teaching methods. Therefore, in order to improve the work of translation, it is recommended to conduct training exercises, conduct question-and-answer conversations or use parts of the text for writing a dictation, a presentation, as well as oral retelling in Russian, which are among the most important stages in the process of Teaching coherent foreign language. The increase in the amount of information that must be conveyed to the student for good assimilation requires the activation of his exchanges between teacher and student, that is, the increasing use of question-answer discussion methods, the division into information flows. In general, the professional competence of a university teacher is a set of skills for structuring scientific and practical knowledge for the optimal solution of educational and pedagogical tasks. The professional competence of a university teacher is a synthesis of professionalism (scientific, special, methodical, psychological and pedagogical training),

creativity (relationship creativity, optimal use of tools, tricks, techniques, teaching methods) and art (acting and public speaking). And today it is becoming clear that it is impossible to "assemble" a competent professional from a simple sum of knowledge, because, moreover, a university teacher must have a great sense of moral responsibility when teaching the modern generation of students.

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